

Enhancing Construction and Demolition Waste Management Programs at NEUST Sumacab Campus: Assessment and Strategic Improvements

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ABSTRACT: Construction waste management is crucial for sustainable urban development. At NEUST Sumacab Campus, effective waste handling is essential to minimize environmental impact. This study evaluates the efficiency of the current construction and demolition waste (CDW) management system and identifies areas for improvement. A structured approach was used, incorporating surveys and site observations. Data were gathered from key stakeholders, including NEUST's Infrastructure and Development Office, contractors, engineers, architects, and foremen, to assess perceptions and practices.

Findings indicate that while some aspects of the waste management system are functional, the overall effectiveness is low, with a rating of 2.47, classified as "rarely." The study highlights the need for improved recycling efforts and better waste management strategies to enhance sustainability on campus. Strengthening waste segregation, recycling, and disposal methods can significantly improve environmental outcomes. These insights contribute to developing a more efficient construction waste management program for NEUST Sumacab Campus, promoting sustainable construction practices.

KEYWORDS: Construction and Demolition Waste, Recycling, waste management practices, waste management program, Construction debris

I. INTRODUCTION

Waste generation is a growing global concern, with construction and demolition waste (CDW) accounting for over 40% of total waste worldwide. By 2025, CDW is expected to reach 2.2 billion tons annually, posing environmental challenges. Addressing this issue aligns with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities), SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production), and SDG 13 (Climate Action) by promoting sustainable waste management, recycling, and reduced landfill use.

In the Philippines, rapid infrastructure growth under the Build Better More (BBM) program has led to increased CDW, yet existing waste management policies, such as Republic Act No. 9003, primarily focus on general solid waste. In Nueva Ecija, particularly in Cabanatuan City, no structured CDW management program exists despite ongoing urbanization.

At NEUST Sumacab Campus, construction waste is not part of the current Material Recovery Facility (MRF) operations, leaving disposal responsibilities to the Infrastructure and Development Office (IDO). This study aims to assess the campus's CDW management practices, identify gaps, and develop a structured waste management program. The proposed initiative will integrate sustainable

practices into the university's existing system, ensuring long-term environmental benefits. Ultimately, this research will lead to a formal CDW management policy, benefiting NEUST by improving waste handling, promoting sustainability, and aligning with national and global environmental goals.

A. General Objective

This study aims to assess the effectiveness of the current construction waste management system at NEUST Sumacab Campus, identify areas for improvement, and develop a sustainable waste management program that promotes waste reuse, recycling, and responsible disposal in alignment with the campus's Material Recovery Facility.

B. Specific Objective

1. Evaluate the current construction waste management system at NEUST Sumacab Campus, Cabanatuan City;
2. Determine whether it efficiently manages the construction waste volume;
3. Identify gaps and areas for improvement that can lead to a more sustainable environment and;
4. Develop a sustainable waste management program at NEUST Sumacab Campus, focusing on waste reuse, recycling, and responsible disposal practices for CDW in

“Enhancing Construction and Demolition Waste Management Programs at NEUST Sumacab Campus: Assessment and Strategic Improvements”

line with the existing Material Recovery and Facility of the campus which focuses on solid waste.

Sometimes	2.61 - 3.40	3
Rarely	1.81 - 2.60	2
Never	1.00 - 1.80	1

II. METHODOLOGY

Figure I. Research Flow

This study follows a descriptive research design to develop a Construction and Demolition Waste (C&D) Management Program at NEUST Sumacab Campus. The research begins with data collection through questionnaires, interviews, and field observations involving key stakeholders such as contractors, project engineers, site architects, foremen, and NEUST representatives.

The survey questionnaire is developed based on a review of existing waste management studies, guidelines, and best practices. A pilot survey is conducted to test and refine the questionnaire, ensuring its reliability and validity. After finalizing the survey instrument, the final survey is administered to a limited number of respondents, using a census sampling method. Since the study focuses on ongoing construction projects, the total number of respondents is expected to be less than 50, eliminating the need for traditional sampling and ensuring that all relevant stakeholders are represented.

The collected data undergoes statistical analysis using descriptive statistics, weighted mean, and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to identify trends, evaluate stakeholder perspectives, and assess significant differences in waste management practices. The weighted mean is computed to measure stakeholder perceptions based on the following rating scale:

Table I Rating Scale

Verbal Description	Weighted Mean Range	Scale
Always	4.21 - 5.00	5
Often	3.41 - 4.20	4

The ANOVA test is used to determine whether significant differences exist between respondents' years of experience and their approach to construction waste management. This will help in understanding variations in waste handling practices among different stakeholder groups.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The socio-demographic profile of the respondents showed that most were school employees (53.80%) working in the Infrastructure and Development Office (IDO) and had 2-10 years of experience (53.80%). The assessment of the current construction waste management system at NEUST Sumacab Campus indicated a high level of effectiveness (mean = 4.52, "Always"), with material quality checks (5.00) and coordination between project heads and workers (4.77) being the most consistently practiced. However, the willingness to use recycled materials (3.92, "Often") suggests room for improvement.

Recycling efforts varied by material type. Concrete recycling was the most common (2.87, "Sometimes"), while glass recycling was nearly nonexistent (1.40, "Never"). Metals, ceramics, wood, plastic pipes, and plumbing fixtures were rarely recycled, highlighting the need for better waste utilization. An ANOVA test found no significant difference ($p = 0.865$) between respondents' years of experience and their perception of the waste management system.

To address gaps, a Proposed Construction Waste Management Program was developed using the Integrated Sustainable Waste Management (ISWM) approach. The program aligns with NEUST's Material Recovery Facility (MRF) and focuses on improving policies, planning, and collaboration between contractors and NEUST personnel to enhance waste management and recycling efforts on campus.

Figure II Effectiveness of Current Waste Management Practices

“Enhancing Construction and Demolition Waste Management Programs at NEUST Sumacab Campus: Assessment and Strategic Improvements”

Figure III – Waste Recycling Practices by Material Type

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig. (p-value)	Interpretation
Between Groups	0.048	3	0.016	0.241	0.865	No Significant Difference
Within Groups	0.597	9	0.066			
Total	0.645	12				

Table II – Result of ANOVA The significance value ($p = 0.865$) is greater than 0.05, meaning there is no significant difference between years of experience and waste management effectiveness.

CONCLUSIONS

This study assessed the effectiveness of the construction and demolition waste (CDW) management system at NEUST Sumacab Campus, focusing on current practices, efficiency, and areas for improvement. Responses from 13 construction professionals, including contractors, engineers, architects, and foremen, revealed that coordination between project heads and workers (mean = 4.77) and proper storage and segregation (mean > 4.3) were highly effective. However, actual recycling efforts varied, with concrete being the most commonly recycled material (mean = 4.15), while metals, wood, plastics, and glass were rarely recycled (mean < 2.5), highlighting gaps in waste utilization.

To improve CDW management, the study recommends that, instead of contractors hauling their waste, the Infrastructure and Development Office (IDO) and NEUST’s Materials Recovery Facility (MRF) collaborate to store, segregate, and reuse materials. This approach benefits contractors by reducing hauling expenses and effort while providing the university with reusable materials for small-scale projects like repairs and landscaping. By retaining

CDW, NEUST can enhance sustainability efforts and reduce costs associated with new construction materials, fostering a more efficient and eco-friendly waste management system.

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“Enhancing Construction and Demolition Waste Management Programs at NEUST Sumacab Campus: Assessment and Strategic Improvements”

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